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The Scope and Dynamics of Pastoral Counselling

Donald A. ODELEYE, PhD

Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

odeleye.bidemi@lcu.edu.ng, +2348060162719

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0917-2883>

Abstract

There is a dearth of scholarly writings on pastoral counselling as a different concept from pastoral care. Most Nigerian theological seminaries and departments of religious studies' curricula are centred on pastoral care. Pastoral counselling, a specialized branch of counselling psychology, is dedicated to assisting individuals in resolving life challenges and emotional issues, ultimately leading to a more fulfilled existence. Rooted in the intersection of biblical theology and psychology, pastoral counselling aims to enhance humanity's comprehension of behavioural and personality dynamics. By integrating spiritual and psychological elements, it provides comprehensive support and guidance to individuals in resolving personal and relational issues, among others. Thus, this study delves into the antecedents, various perspectives, theoretical frameworks, clinical assessment methods, scope, and prospects of pastoral counselling. The author contends that pastoral counselling holds the potential to facilitate humanity's spiritual restoration.

Keywords: Behaviour, pastoral counselling, psychological theories

Introduction

Pastoral Counselling is the specialised aspect of Counselling Psychology that links divinity with humanity. It is the interconnectivity of theology and psychology with the primary aim of helping people cope with issues of life (Worthington 2014). The pastoral counsellor leverages psychological theories, principles and practices to resolve human emotional, social and psychological concerns. They provide support and guidance on many issues, including marital choice, relationships, spiritual confusion and exploration, family cohesion, bereavement, and sibling rivalry, among others. It involves applying knowledge of psychological principles and skills to the ministry of providing clinical pastoral care for people within and outside the faith community.

The pastoral counsellor, in helping people deal with various challenges of life, is concerned with three major aspects: spiritual health, mental health and physical health. Since the spiritual is ahead of the physical, and the unseen precedes the seen, it is taken that mental wellness may be a function of one's spiritual wellness. It is within the soulful realm that cognition and emotions are developed.

Pastoral counselling seeks to integrate spiritual, emotional, and relational dimensions of human life. It recognizes that mental health is related to people's faith, community, and personal well-being. In contemporary times, where fragmentation and disconnection are prevalent, pastoral counselling offers holistic support for wholesome living. Pastoral counselling is interested in gaining knowledge and understanding of the psychological needs and experiences of people

within the context of faith, religion, and culture. The pastoral counsellor is committed to the integration of faith into a life of wholeness for people (Odeleye 2022). Religious leaders and pastoral counsellors collaborate in providing people with the spiritual and psychological education they need to cope better in life. Religious and cultural sensitivity are expedient for the effective pastoral counsellor. The therapist should always be sensitive to the beliefs and faith of their clientele.

Antecedents

Historically, pastoral counselling may be as old as humanity since its thrust is assisting others to make decisions that will lead to more fulfilling life outcomes through the lens of divinity (Odeleye 2017). As a profession and academic discipline, pastoral counselling is reputed to have evolved in the United States of America through the initiative of Rev. Anton Theophilus Boisen, who started clinical pastoral counselling with his theology students. Rev. Anton Theophilus Boisen is indeed considered one of the pioneering figures in pastoral psychology. His contributions have significantly shaped the field, particularly in the context of clinical pastoral education (CPE). Boisen is recognized as the founder of the clinical pastoral education movement. He was the first clergy member to supervise students in what we now know as CPE. He believed in the importance of firsthand study of human experience to challenge seminarians' theological thinking. Rather than relying solely on classroom training, he emphasized engaging with "living human documents.

Boisen's approach shifted theological training from a focus on the past to a present-centered, experiential approach. The parish became the laboratory, and individual needs took precedence. Boisen's personal experiences with mental illness (he had several episodes of schizophrenia) influenced his theological perspective. He sought to bridge the gap between science (medicine) and religion. His work emphasized empirical inquiry into the theology of sin and salvation. For Boisen, salvation meant being incorporated into the "Beloved Community emphasizing community as central to theological thought. Boisen pioneered the establishment of pastoral care in psychiatry. He recognized that spiritual health and caring for a patient's soul were integral components of psychological well-being. His work challenged traditional religious views by proposing connections between religious experiences and certain forms of mental illness. Rev. Anton Boisen's legacy lies in his innovative approach to theological education, his emphasis on experiential learning, and his commitment to understanding the human predicament through the lens of faith and community.

Pastoral counsellors help others to cope better with life and its challenges leveraging the spiritual aspects of their personality. They help their client to become a better version of their present self by exposing them to causative issues in asocial behaviour, the coping techniques needed to mitigate certain behaviours, and the dynamics of maintaining optimal mental health. Areas of concern for pastoral counsellors include (but are not limited to) premarital, marital, and post-marital issues, relationships, intimate partner violence, traumatic life events such as ageing, divorce, bereavement, illness, and job loss. There are several psychosocial theories and therapies pastoral counsellors use to help people. These may include social learning, psychoanalysis, humanistic therapy, and cognitive behaviour therapy, among others.

Perspectives in Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral counselling is an interdisciplinary field that focuses on the understanding of human psyche and spiritual well-being. It combines elements of psychology and spirituality to provide holistic support and guidance to individuals.

The origins of pastoral counselling can be traced back to early religious practices, where spiritual leaders were responsible for providing guidance and support to their communities. Over time, this role evolved to incorporate psychological principles and techniques, leading to the development of pastoral psychology as a distinct field. Today, pastoral counselling draws from various disciplines, including education, psychology, counselling, and theology, to offer a comprehensive approach to understanding and addressing human needs.

Even though pastoral counsellors may be as varied as the religions and persuasions in the world, they typically agree on the place of the supernatural in humanity's creation and sustenance. They seem unequivocal that there is a supreme being overseeing the universe. They also generally posit that central to humanity's challenge is disobedience to God. The question of SIN is a recurring decimal in pastoral counselling. It is this author's perspective that all will be well with humanity if they return to their "manufacturer".

There are two primary perspectives in pastoral psychology: the spiritual perspective and the psychological perspective, and the two have variants, the moderate and the hyper. The spiritual perspective is a continuum that emphasizes the importance of faith, belief systems, and religious practices in promoting mental and emotional well-being. The moderate-spiritual perspective leverages psychological theories, skills, and practices for therapy while the hyper-spiritual perspective rarely utilizes psychology in counselling. On the other hand, the psychological perspective is a continuum that focuses on understanding human thoughts, emotions, and behaviours through psychological theories and concepts. The moderate psychological perspective engages the holy books and other religious rituals for counselling intervention, but the hyper-psychological perspective deemphasizes religious rites in their counselling relationships. However, the holistic integration of both perspectives in pastoral counselling may allow for a comprehensive understanding of individuals' spiritual and psychological needs.

The Effective Pastoral Counsellor

There are two critical things in the effective delivery of pastoral counselling services: the pastoral counsellor and the therapeutic process. Pastoral counselling is not just about offering advice; it is a skilled practice that thrives on a unique blend of personal qualities, professional development, and a deep understanding of the religious context (Hunter 2017). Among other qualities, the pastoral counsellor must demonstrate empathy, active listening, knowledge of God, good communication skills, mastery of the scriptures, interpersonal skills, and the capacity to keep secrets secret.

Empathic Connection

Effective counsellors demonstrate genuine empathy, a cornerstone for building trust and rapport. By stepping into the counsellee's shoes, they create a safe space for vulnerability and open communication, fostering the groundwork for healing.

Active Listening

Beyond simply hearing words, pastoral counsellors actively listen. This involves attentive focus, allowing the counsellee to express themselves freely without interruption. Through active listening, counsellors can identify underlying issues and concerns, building trust and demonstrating genuine care.

Rooted in Faith

A deep love for their faith and a personal relationship with God are essential for pastoral counsellors. Their own spiritual journey equips them to guide and support others, drawing from their faith to provide wisdom, hope, and encouragement.

Bridging the Gap

Effective communication is a two-way street. Pastoral counsellors must express themselves clearly, using language that resonates with the counsellee's background and understanding. This includes translating biblical principles and spiritual truths into relatable concepts that can be applied to everyday life.

Scriptural Expertise

Understanding and explaining God's Word is a unique ability of pastoral counsellors. They utilize Scripture as a source of guidance, comfort, and encouragement during sessions, drawing from its wisdom to address the specific needs of each counsellee.

Synergy is Key

Pastoral counsellors don't work in isolation. Collaboration with other members of the faith community, such as church leaders, support groups, and ministries, is essential. This team approach allows for a holistic care plan, providing multifaceted support for individuals and families.

Confidentiality

Maintaining confidentiality is paramount. Pastoral counsellors must create a safe space where individuals feel comfortable sharing their struggles without fear of judgment or gossip. Upholding confidentiality builds trust and encourages open communication.

Pastoral counselling stands at the intersection of psychological insights and spiritual guidance. It's a unique blend of mental healthcare and faith-based support, offering a holistic approach to address the multifaceted needs of those seeking help. By effectively balancing these aspects, pastoral counsellors can provide transformative care that empowers individuals on their journey towards healing and growth.

Effective Pastoral Counselling Services Delivery

Pastoral counsellors use several methods to help their clients to regain self-mastery and become better versions of themselves. A combination of assessment and diagnosis, prayer, meditation, the sacred scriptures, and fasting may be deployed to help their counselees, depending on the problems they are dealing with. Specifically, the pastoral counsellor should create a safe and supportive environment for their clientele, undertake a clinical assessment, diagnosis, treatment and referral.

Create a Safe and Supportive Environment

The first line of intervention in pastoral counselling is to create a safe and supportive environment for the client. The counsellor will seek to build rapport with the client, winning their trust and enjoying their confidence. The client should be accorded “unconditional positive regard”. The motive of the counsellor is to win the heart of the client so that the counselling encounter will be successful. This experience may take a few days, depending on the severity of the case at hand. Thus, it will allow the therapist to further blend with the client.

Clinical Assessment

While it is expected that more counselling interviews should be client-centred, with the counsellee taking the lead in expressing themselves, the therapist should guide the client with questions and rapt attention. The clinical interview is an in-depth conversation to elicit information on the client’s faith, background, and life concerns, among others. The client discusses freely about their beliefs, faith, and concerns.

Clinical assessment in pastoral counselling involves the use of various techniques and tools to evaluate an individual's spiritual and psychological well-being. These may include interviews, psychological tests, and assessments of religious and spiritual practices. Holistic assessment is crucial in pastoral counselling, as it considers both the spiritual and psychological aspects of an individual's life, providing a comprehensive understanding of their needs and challenges. The assessment should lead to a diagnosis of the challenge the client is dealing with.

Diagnosis

The counsellor explores the client's strengths, coping mechanisms, and existing support systems such as family, faith, and community. After gathering as much information on the client, the therapist should be able to identify the main needs of the counsellee and thereafter prepare an intervention plan.

Treatment

The counsellor and client work together to establish goals for therapy, considering both spiritual and psychological well-being of the client. The plan should incorporate spiritual strategies, including prayer, scripture study, memorization of scriptures, or participation in religious activities to promote growth. Depending on the counselor's training and the client's needs, techniques like active listening, cognitive-behavioural therapy, mindfulness, or breathing

exercises might be used. In all, pastoral counselling offers a unique approach to mental and emotional well-being, acknowledging the importance of faith and spirituality in people's lives.

Referral

If necessary, the counsellor may refer the client to another mental health professional for further assessment and/or treatment.

Some Theories in Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral Counsellors draw from various theoretical frameworks to guide the counselling process. They engage different psychological orientations as they delve into the study of human personality and mental health over different parameters (Augsburger 1989, Odeleye 2008). Specifically, we shall be looking at some personality theories, mental health theories, and interpersonal relationship theories.

Personality Theories

These are frameworks that explain why individuals behave the way they do. These theories elucidate why some traits are dominant in particular persons and not in others.

- **Psychoanalytic Theory:** This classic theory propounded by Sigmund Freud, proposes a three-part personality structure: id (primitive desires), ego (mediates id and superego), and superego (internalized moral compass). It emphasizes childhood experiences and unconscious motivations (Friedman 2017).
- **Trait Theory:** This approach (which is also called The Big 5 Theory) focuses on identifying core personality traits like extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience. These traits are seen as relatively stable across situations (McCrae & Costa 1999).

Mental Health Theories:

- **Biological Theories:** These theories explain mental health issues through the lens of brain chemistry, genetics, and neurophysiology. For example, imbalances in neurotransmitters like serotonin are linked to depression (American Psychiatric Association 2013).
- **Psychological Theories:** These theories focus on how our thoughts, emotions, and behaviours contribute to mental health. Cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) is a prominent example, aiming to change negative thought patterns that contribute to emotional distress (Beck 1976).
- **Social Learning Theories:** These theories propose that mental health can be impacted by social factors like stress, trauma, and social support. For instance, it is suggested that social isolation can exacerbate depression (Turner 2003).

Interpersonal Relationship Theories

- **Attachment Theory:** John Bowlby's theory suggests that early childhood attachment to caregivers shapes how people form relationships later in life. Secure attachments lead to healthier and more trusting relationships, while insecure attachments can contribute to difficulties in intimacy and emotional regulation (Bowlby 1982).

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- **Social Exchange Theory:** This theory proposes that relationships are formed and maintained based on a cost-benefit analysis. People seek relationships that offer rewards and satisfaction while minimizing costs (Kelly & Thibaut (1978).
 - **Social Penetration Theory:** This theory describes how relationships develop through layers of self-disclosure. As people share more personal information and experiences, intimacy deepens (Altman & Taylor 1973).

Some Areas of Intervention

Pastoral counsellors work with people from diverse backgrounds and virtually all works of life (Clinebell 2011). They also provide spiritual and emotional support to people dealing with a variety of challenges. Some of the areas of pastoral counselling intervention are as follows:

- **Grief and loss:** For people who have lost loved ones, or jobs, the pastoral counsellor is handy to help them cope with their emotions and find meaning in their loss.
- **Marital and family problems:** Pastoral counsellors can help couples and families communicate more effectively, resolve conflicts, and strengthen their relationships.
- **Mental health issues:** Depending on the extent of training, pastoral counsellors may be able to provide support and guidance to people struggling with anxiety, depression, and other mental health challenges.
- **Life transitions:** Pastoral counsellors can help people adjust to major life changes, such as serious illness, accident, retirement, or a new baby.
- **Spiritual concerns:** Pastoral counsellors can help to explore their faith, deal with doubt, or find comfort in difficult times.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Pastoral counsellors and therapists work with individuals, couples, and families to address spiritual and psychological concerns, providing support and guidance based on their unique needs. Additionally, pastoral counselling plays a vital role in community support and advocacy, offering outreach programmes, crisis intervention, and support groups to promote overall well-being within communities.

Looking toward the future, pastoral counselling faces emerging trends and challenges. The increasing diversity in religious and spiritual practices calls for a greater understanding and respect for different belief systems. Additionally, the integration of technology in therapy and counselling presents both opportunities and challenges in maintaining the personal and spiritual connection between counsellor and client. Despite these challenges, there is immense potential for the growth and development of pastoral counselling, as society continues to recognize the importance of addressing spiritual and psychological needs holistically. It is expected that pastoral counsellors should work more with a network of other helping professionals such as social workers, nurses, doctors, psychiatrists, and clinical psychologists, among others. This will help them maximise their impact on the community they are called to serve. In all, pastoral counselling can restore humanity to Edenic purity as it helps people to find peace and tranquillity in God.

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